

Mapping the circular economy context within the curricula in the field of Industrial Engineering - comparative study of degree programs in two Polish universities

Tomasz Nitkiewicz¹, Magdalena Wojnarowska²

¹ Department of Business Informatics and Ecosystems, Faculty of Management, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland

² Department of Product Technology and Ecology, Institute of Quality Science and Product Management, Cracow University of Economics

Email: tomasz.nitkiewicz@pcz.pl; wojnarom@uek.krakow.pl

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5095699>

Abstract

Streamlining the circular economy (CE) topic across the industries has significant mobilizing effect on academic curricula. New programs, new courses and its topics are being introduced in order to provide knowledge and skills that are appropriate to handle circularity challenge. The objective of the paper is to investigate the issue from the perspective of Industrial Engineering field of knowledge and academic programs. The objective of the paper is to develop the framework to compare the coverage for CE related issues, and subsequently to verify it within the degree programs of two Polish universities: Cracow University of Economics (CUE) and Czestochowa University of Technology (CUT). The comparison is based on the content of the following building blocks of curricula: objectives, program learning outcomes, graduate profile description, courses and course learning outcomes. The group of programs included within the analysis consists of the ones that are tightly related to Industrial Engineering but are defined individually by the Universities. The bachelor programs of Quality and Production Management (CUT) and Management and Production Engineering (CUE) are in the core of comparison. The comparison aims also in mapping the CE related skills and competences within compared programs.

Keywords: Circular Economy; Industrial Engineering; Industrial Engineering Degree Programs; Circular Economy Education.

1 Introduction

1.1 Circular Economy concept and its building blocks

The circular economy (CE) concept has gained increasing attention from global policymakers, which has also turned into more in-depth definition of the concept and underlying mechanism. Despite the common engagement of regulators and scientist the features of CE or its implementation conditions and requirements are yet not clearly defined.

The most widespread definition of CE is that published by Ellen MacArthur Foundation, where CE is defined as „an industrial system that is restorative or regenerative by intention and design. It replaces the ‘end-of-life’ concept with restoration, shifts towards the use of renewable energy, eliminates the use of toxic chemicals, which impair reuse, and aims for the elimination of waste through the superior design of materials, products, systems, and, within this, business models” (EMF, 2013).

Kirchherr et al. (2017), after distilling from over one hundred of definitions, defined CE as: an “economic system that is based on business models which replace the ‘end-of-life’ concept with reducing, alternatively reusing, recycling and recovering materials in production/distribution and consumption processes, thus operating at the micro level (products, companies, consumers), meso level (eco-industrial parks) and macro level (city, region, nation and beyond), with the aim to accomplish sustainable development, which implies creating environmental quality, economic prosperity and social equity, to the benefit of current and future generations”. Murray et al. (2017) has defined CE as “an economic model wherein planning, resourcing, procurement, production and reprocessing are designed and managed, as both process and output, to maximize ecosystem functioning and human well-being”. Since our approach is based on referring CE concept to the fields of knowledge in higher education, it is important to summarize these definitions from the perspective of its

contributing fields and building blocks. These fundamental building blocks of CE in Europe are grouped under eight headlines as (1) industrial symbiosis, 2) material resource efficiency, 3) product life-cycle extension, 4) biological products, 5) energy efficiency and renewable energy, 6) the performance economy, 7) the sharing economy and 8) the platform economy (Taranic, Behrens, & Topi, 2016).

As proposed by Circle Economy organization the core elements of CE transition are: prioritize regenerative resources, stretch the lifetime and use waste as a resource. The key enablers to achieve that are named as: rethink the business model, team up to create joint value, design for the future, incorporate digital technology and strengthen & advance knowledge (Goodwin Brown et al., 2021).

1.2 Referring CE to the field of knowledge

According to Türkeli et al. (2018) CE research is originating from the following fields of knowledge: Environmental Sciences, Environmental Engineering, Energy & Fuels, Management, Geography and Urban Studies, Economics, Industrial Engineering, Manufacturing Engineering, Thermodynamics, Chemical Engineering, Biotechnology, Agricultural Engineering, Water Resources. The classification of fields of knowledge to the specific building blocks of CE concept is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Coverage of CE building blocks within fields of knowledge

Building blocks of CE	Major fields of knowledge	Minor fields of knowledge
industrial symbiosis	Environmental Engineering Industrial Engineering Manufacturing Engineering	Environmental Sciences Energy & Fuels Management Geography and Urban Studies Chemical Engineering Biotechnology Agricultural Engineering
material resource efficiency	Environmental Engineering Manufacturing Engineering	Energy & Fuels Industrial Engineering Thermodynamics Chemical Engineering Agricultural Engineering Water Resources
product life-cycle extension	Industrial Engineering	Management Manufacturing Engineering
biological products	Environmental Sciences Biotechnology Agricultural Engineering	Environmental Engineering Chemical Engineering Water Resources
energy efficiency and renewable energy	Energy & Fuels Thermodynamics	Environmental Engineering Industrial Engineering Chemical Engineering Biotechnology Agricultural Engineering

		Water Resources
performance economy	Management Economics	Energy & Fuels Industrial Engineering Manufacturing Engineering Agricultural Engineering
sharing economy	Economics	Management Geography and Urban Studies
platform economy	Management	Economics

The objective of the paper is to propose an assessment framework to investigate the issue from the perspective of Industrial Engineering field of knowledge and academic programs. Since, no such methods or studies has been proposed so far, the paper is aiming at signaling the coverage of CE concept within existing academic programs with a proposed mapping approach. The objective of the paper is supported through the comparison of the degree and master programs of two Polish universities: Cracow University of Economics (CUE) and Czestochowa University of Technology (CUT). The assessment and comparison method is based on the content of the following building blocks of curricula: objectives, program learning outcomes (PLOs), graduate profile description, courses and course learning outcomes (CLOs).

2 Mapping CE context within selected programs

2.1 Characteristics of the investigated programs

According to the Türkeli et al. (2018) industrial engineering (IE) is one of the fields of knowledge that addresses the issue of CE and its application. The programs that are selected for comparison are Management and Production Engineering (CUE) (UEK, 2021) and Quality and Production Management (CUT) (CUT, 2017). According to the classification proposed by Lima et al. (2012) both of these programs belong to IE field of knowledge but at the same time at its core the fields of management and manufacturing engineering are also covered (Nitkiewicz et al., 2020). Therefore, both of the programs should be providing graduates with appropriate competences to deal with managerial and IE aspects of CE solution implementation. The two programs are considered from the perspective of CE concept and its underlying building blocks. The basic characteristics of the two selected programs is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The comparison of basic characteristics of the two selected degree programs

Characteristics	Management and Production Engineering CUE	Quality and Production Management CUT
Level	Degree program (engineer)	Degree program (engineer)
No. of Years / Semesters	3,5 / 7	3,5 / 7
No. of ECTS*	221	210
No. of Course Hours (contact hours)	2100	2404
No. of Courses**	47	68
No. of PLOs (Knowledge/Competences/Social skills)	5/7/5	10/11/5

** European Credit Transfer System (ECTS) - is a standardised credit system of the European Higher Education Area for better recognition of students' academic qualifications and study programs and possible exchange periods abroad

* refers to number of courses, both obligatory and electable, required finish the degree

According to ECTS a degree program consists of either 180 or 240 credits for 3 or 4 years programs, respectively. Since both of the programs considered are 3,5 years long the nominal ECTS credits ceiling is 210, but with MPE program it is exceeded with additional courses. As indicated in the Table 2, the PLOs are divided into three categories: knowledge, competences and social skills. In general, social skills should be out of the scope of CE related education and competence building, since they are universal and indifferent concerning the scope of its application.

The objectives of the curricula, as stated within program documentation, does not refer directly to CE concept, but mention several fields of education that are related to CE (mostly the field of industrial engineering and management, as well as its elements). It seems that CE concept at its complexity is not addressed intentionally neither in QPM nor in MPE curriculum. Similar case is for graduate profiles that are referred to the industrial fields and set of competences appropriate for CE implementation in both investigated curricula.

2.2 Mapping CE context within PLOs of selected programs

The comparative analysis of PLOs is based on CE specific criteria that are divided into direct and indirect category. The elements belonging to these categories are further classified with regard to their reference to CE concept. The methodology of classification is presented on Figure 2. By direct reference we mean the use of CE concept itself or its building blocks in an element of curriculum. By indirect reference we mean the use of term that could be underlying prerequisite or necessary condition for the CE concept or its building blocks implementation. The distinction between the content and approach alignment to CE is made upon the way curriculum elements are presented. CE content is generally covering its building blocks while CE approach is matched with CE enablers. The symbols used to denote the reference on Figure 2 are composed of the part indicating its type (CA – content and approach; C – content; A – approach) and the part indicating its strength of CE concept support with the scale of 1 to 5, where 1 indicates the highest possible contribution to CE knowledge and skill set, while 5 indicates the lowest possible, but still contributing factors.

Figure 2. Type of reference of academic programs to CE concept

Figure 3 and Figure 4 map the relationship of PLOs of investigated degree programs to CE concept. The denotation used here refers to three different types of learning outcomes: knowledge (denoted as W), competences (U) and social skills (K). The PLOs are numbered according to their appearance order in program documentations. The map is based on the criteria presented in Figure 2. According to the classification, each PLO is qualified to the category of content, approach or content and approach reference, which is in the following step assessed with regard to its directness towards CE. The size of the bubbles is representing the

significance of given PLO for the whole program. This is measured by the number of references to given PLO in course syllabuses. The more references the better coverage for given PLO within the program.

To get an overview of the PLOs that are highly contributing to CE education two of them that are classified as the most significant in a sense of its contribution are presented below:

Student has basic knowledge to understand mutual influence of phenomena and processes of economic, legal, organizational and engineering character that occur in companies

[PLO W02 from QPM (CUT)]

Students knows and understands the processes occurring in life cycle of machines, objects and technical systems. Additionally, student has knowledge on materials, technologies and tools used for solving engineering type of problems related to Management and Production Engineering field of knowledge

[PLO W04 from MPE (CUE)]

The content issues within the two PLOs is related to industrial processes (W02 QPM) and necessary equipment and infrastructure to run them (W04 MPE). The approach that is appropriate to CE concept is presented by interrelation of "economic, legal, organizational and engineering character" (W02 QPM) and life cycle approach (W04 MPE).

Figure 3. The reference of PLOs to the CE concept: program of Quality and Production Management (CUT)

Figure 4. The reference of PLOs to the CE concept: program of Management and Production Engineering (CUE)

While interpreting maps on Figure 3 and Figure 4 we should also spot the strong contribution of CA PLOs within both programs. These groups consist of W02 and U06 and W01, W05, W08 and U06 for MPE and QPM programs, respectively. The direct support for CE related knowledge and skills is more developed within QPM programs with a set of C (U10 and K03) and A (W09) PLOs. The remaining group of PLOs could only slightly contribute to CE competence and knowledge building or have no significant impact at all.

The mapping framework developed here shows a potential to assess and compare the programs with regard to its CE preparedness capacity. On the other hand, the use of ordinal classification parameters leads to the clustering of PLOs and, in a consequence, difficulties in detailed interpretation of the data. The transformation of ordinal parameters to continuous variables could bring the important breakthrough in reading the data.

2.3 Mapping the CE context within course structure and CLOs

The following step of analysis is related to the courses included in the two analyzed programs. From the perspective of the potential contribution to CE concept the courses has been classified as related, potentially related and unrelated ones. Table 1 presents the results of courses classification and includes three classification levels and considers courses specific for both of selected programs as well as courses that are common for both of them. In the case of the courses with the same names it is just written in appropriate cell of QPM & MPE row. In case of the courses with supposedly same content but different names it is denoted with the slash symbol ("/"). Occurrence of "&" symbol indicates the two courses that fit together to the topic of one course form another program. Both programs have the similar number of courses that are classified as directly related to CE concept. Three out of these courses are the same or very similar within both programs. These courses cover environmental management, waste management and logistics issues. QPM CUT program has also course on sustainable management and on process and product innovation that are classified as directly related. MPE CUE program has also course on biotechnology, on production system design and on cleaner production.

Table 1. Classification of courses with regard to their relationship to CE concept

Programs	Courses		
	Directly related	Potentially related	Unrelated
QPM	Sustainable management Process and product innovation	Materials in production processes Operational research investment projects Intelligent SMART Metering system Theory of machines Safety of process installations	Industrial property management Statistics in production Sociology Negotiation and mediation techniques Production scheduling and control

		ERP Management support system Lean Manufacturing Documentation of quality and work safety systems Quality control in special processes Computer simulation of manufacturing processes Management of machinery and equipment operation Engineering project Transport infrastructure management Energy efficiency management Production systems Commodity science Virtual enterprises	Statistical process control Ergonomics Six sigma Technological resources
QPE & MPE	Environmental management system / Ecology of natural resources and environmental management Industrial waste management / Waste Management Production Logistics / Corporate Logistics	Business-to business-marketing / Marketing Economic law / Business Law Macroeconomics Production processes and technologies Microeconomics Production and service management Quality management & Work safety management / Quality and Safety Management Introduction to automation of production processes / Automation of production processes Engineering project management Fundamentals of engineering design / Machine Construction and Engineering Designing Computer support for engineering projects / IT and Computer-Aided Methods for Engineering Work	Accounting for manufacturing companies & The Cost Account for Engineers / Accounting Mathematics Physics Finance Business management basic Information technology Fundamentals of metrology / Metrology Engineering and technical drawing / Engineering Graphics Physical Education Methods of business organization and management / Basics of Organization and Management Human Resources Management
MPE	Biotechnology Production System Designing The Technologies and Organization of Cleaner Production	Chemistry Business ethics The Knowledge of Materials and Light Industrial Engineering The Knowledge of Materials and Plastics Engineering Vegetable Food Processing Processing Food of Animal Origin Packaging techniques Microbiological Industrial Threats Operational Management	Physics The Protection of Intellectual Property The Basics of Mechanics and Strength of Materials Statistics

The last part of the analysis refers to the objectives and learning outcomes of the courses that are supposedly related to CE concept. The classification is presented in Table 2. The classification of contents is based of the ratio of teaching hours that are related to CE concept and its underlying building blocks. The classification of course objective (CO) and course learning outcomes (CLOs) is based on the same assumptions as the one used for PLOs. As shown in Table 2 the direct, not all of the courses maintain to keep the direct link to CE concept (examples of *Process and product innovation* and *Logistics* courses) or keep it only through the content and not the approach (*Production system design*). Not surprisingly, environmental management and waste management courses have the highest capacity and best coverage to contribute to CE related knowledge and

skills. The significance of *Sustainable management* course is somehow undermined by its electable character, nevertheless, it has the third highest contribution.

Table 2. Classification of objectives and learning outcomes of selected courses from QPM and MPE programs

Courses with direct connection to CE concept	QPM		MPE	
	Contents	CO & CLOs	Contents	CO & CLOs
Sustainable management	80,0%	CA2		
Process and product innovation	30,0%	CA4		
Environmental management system / Ecology of natural resources and environmental management	95,8%	CA1	87,0%	CA1
Industrial waste management / Waste Management	93,3%	CA1	100,0%	CA1
Production Logistics / Corporate Logistics	42,9%	CA4	33,3%	CA4
Biotechnology			26,7%	CA2
Production System Designing			37,5%	C3
The Technologies and Organization of Cleaner Production			65,2%	CA2

The approach used for mapping the course structure with regard to the CE context is still missing the aggregation functionality that would enable the complex comparison of the programs. For the moment, the mapping approach proposed is applied to assess PLOs and course structure independently. The next step in its development, and perhaps in wider assessment of industrial engineering programs, is to develop its results synthesizing mechanism and easy-to-use framework for curriculum development and adjustment to CE requirements.

3 Conclusions

As the results of analysis shows, the industrial engineering programs, namely Management and Production Engineering at CUE and Quality and Production Management at CUT, have strong relationship to CE concept but it should be still classified as secondary type of relationship. This is due to relatively weak coverage within PLOs and courses. Some courses are strongly dedicated to CE related content and have pretty wide coverage for CE building blocks. CE concept is not addressed literally, neither within the objectives and PLOs of the programs, nor within dedicated courses.

Since CE plays key roles for industrial economics to pursue sustainable development, it should be indeed acknowledged as capable of harmonizing ambitions favoring not only economic growth but also environmental protection, thereby opposing to the conventional highly-impacting linear model of the economy (Hysa, Kruja, Rehman, & Laurenti, 2020). Such a transformation should be also happening at the level of higher education within industrial engineering and its related fields. The investigated programs have been visibly equipped with toolbox needed to introduce CE solutions but still in non-systemic and partial way. Nevertheless, the key building blocks of CE have significant coverage and potential for further development.

The approach used here for mapping CE content within the degree programs within industrial engineering knowledge area has some limitations. First of all, the mapping process was not referred to the CE benchmark since there is no clear consensus on CE education within IE field. Secondly, the mapping was performed upon the documentation of the two programs and, therefore, had no reference to the students or industry preferences, evaluation of graduates or opinions of academics. This drawback could be easily overcome with completing the study with additional steps but since QPM curriculum has not yet produced its graduates it was not possible at the time of writing the paper.

The assessment and mapping framework is not yet finalized, and as mentioned above, has some significant drawbacks related to the subjectivity of the assessment, lack of results integration functionality and dependence on ordinal variables. The proposed framework should be a starting point of the discussion on introducing CE learning outcomes in industrial engineering programmes and the assessment of its progress methodology.

Funding (Financial Disclosure): The Project has been financed by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education within "Regional Initiative of Excellence" Programme for 2019-2022. Project no.: 021/RID/2018/19. Total financing: 11 897 131,40 PLN.

4 References

- CUT. (2017). Program studiów. Nazwa kierunku: Zarządzanie Jakością i Produkcją.
- EMF. (2013). Towards the circular economy: Economic and business rationale for an accelerated transition. Cowes, UK.
- Goodwin Brown, E., Novak, M., Haigh, L., Birliga, A., Wildi, D., Wynaendts, S., & Dufourmont, J. (2021). Key Elements of the Circular Economy.
- Hysa, E., Kruja, A., Rehman, N. U., & Laurenti, R. (2020). Circular economy innovation and environmental sustainability impact on economic growth: An integrated model for sustainable development. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 12(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU12124831>
- Kirchherr, J., Reike, D., & Hekkert, M. (2017, December 1). Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, Vol. 127, pp. 221–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.09.005>
- Lima, R. M., Mesquita, D., Amorim, M., Jonker, G., & Flores, M. A. (2012). An Analysis of Knowledge Areas in Industrial Engineering and Management Curriculum. *International Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management (IJIEEM)*, 3(2), 75–82.
- Murray, A., Skene, K., & Haynes, K. (2017). The Circular Economy: An Interdisciplinary Exploration of the Concept and Application in a Global Context. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 140(3), 369–380. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-015-2693-2>
- Nitkiewicz, T., Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya, D., Koszewska, M., Wiszumirska, K., Wojnarowska, M., & Koomsap, P. (2020). LOVE model-based assessment of teaching practices within industrial engineering master programs in Poland and Thailand. In R. M. Lima, V. Villas-Boas, K. Sethanan, & P. Koomsap (Eds.), *Proceedings of the PAEE/ALE'2020, International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education*; (pp. 165–173). Patuthani, Thailand: PAEE.
- Taranic, I., Behrens, A., & Topi, C. (2016). Understanding the Circular Economy in Europe , from Resource Efficiency to Sharing Platforms: The CEPS Framework. In *Ceps Special Report*.
- Türkeli, S., Kemp, R., Huang, B., Bleischwitz, R., & McDowall, W. (2018). Circular economy scientific knowledge in the European Union and China: A bibliometric, network and survey analysis (2006–2016). *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 197(June), 1244–1261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.06.118>
- UEK. (2021). <https://uek.krakow.pl/>. Retrieved April 23, 2021, from <https://uek.krakow.pl/>